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***Ophrys molisana* in Abruzzo, Molise and Latium (Central Italy)**

Keywords

Orchidaceae, *Ophrys*, *Ophrys aranifera* of Popoli, *Ophrys dinarica*, *Ophrys insectifera*, *Ophrys molisana*, *Ophrys romolinii*, *Ophrys* × *fucinis*, *Ophrys* × *milioniae*, *Ophrys* × *rasinii*, flora of Abruzzo, Molise and Latium, Central Italy.

Summary

Soca, R. (2017): *Ophrys molisana* in Abruzzo, Molise and Latium (Central Italy).- J. Eur. Orch. 49 (2): 361-386.

Ophrys molisana has recently been described as a new species from the Molise (Central Italy) (DELFORGE 2015). For a better knowledge of this new species, the author presents the results of his field-investigations. The species has a wide distribution in Abruzzo and reaches the region of Lazio. Its variability is illustrated by means of numerous photographs. A first draft of the species distribution in the L'Aquila province (Abruzzo, Italy) is outlined and presented on a distribution map. In addition, three new hybrids having *Ophrys molisana* as one parent are described.

Zusammenfassung

Soca, R. (2017): *Ophrys molisana* in Abruzzen, Molise und Latium (Mittelitalien).- J. Eur. Orch. 49 (2): 361-386.

Ophrys molisana wurde vor kurzem als neue Art aus dem Molise (Mittelitalien) beschrieben (DELFORGE 2015). Zur besseren Kenntnis dieser neuen Art legt der Autor die Ergebnisse umfangreicher Felduntersuchungen vor. Danach besitzt die Art eine weite Verbreitung in den Abruzzen und erreicht auch die Region Latium. Die Variabilität der Art wird anhand zahlreicher Fotos illustriert, die bekannten Funddaten aus den Abruzzen und angrenzenden Regionen werden aufgelistet. Für die Abruzzen wird eine vorläufige Verbreitungskarte erstellt. Drei neue Hybriden mit *Ophrys molisana* werden beschrieben.

Riassunto

Soca, R. (2017): *Ophrys molisana* negli Abruzzi, il Molise ed il Lazio (Italia centrale).- J. Eur. Orch. 49 (2): 361-386.

Ophrys molisana è stata recentemente descritta come una nuova specie del Molise (Italia centrale) (DELFORGE 2015). Per una migliore conoscenza di questa nuova specie, l'autore presenta i risultati di approfondite indagini di campo. La specie ha un'ampia distribuzione in Abruzzo e ha raggiunto la regione Lazio. La variabilità è illustrata con molte foto. Un primo abbozzo della cartografia della specie per la provincia di L'Aquila (Abruzzi, Italia) è schizzata e presentata su una carta di distribuzione. Inoltre, tre ibridi nuovi di cui uno dei genitori è *Ophrys molisana* sono descritti.

Résumé

Soca, R. (2017): *Ophrys molisana* dans les Abruzzes, le Molise et le Latium (Italie centrale).- J. Eur. Orch. 49 (2): 361-386.

Ophrys molisana a récemment été décrit comme une nouvelle espèce du Molise (Italie centrale) (DELFORGE 2015). Pour une meilleure connaissance de cette nouvelle espèce, l'auteur présente les résultats des enquêtes approfondies sur le terrain. L'espèce a une large distribution dans les Abruzzes et atteint la région du Latium. Sa variabilité est illustrée au moyen de nombreuses photos. Une première ébauche de la cartographie de l'espèce pour la province de L'Aquila (Abruzzes, Italie) est esquissée et présentée sur une carte de distribution. En outre, trois nouveaux hybrides dont l'un des parents est *Ophrys molisana* sont décrits.

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1. Introduction

Ophrys molisana is a recently described species (DELFORGE 2015: 18). For a better understanding of this taxon, the author contributes his own point of view about the description of the species, the general characteristics of his natural habitat, the flowering dates and the specific features of this taxon. Its occurrence in the L'Aquila province (Abruzzo, Italy) will then be considered through a list of places in this province. At last, the descriptions of three hybrids having *Ophrys molisana* as one of their parents will be submitted.

2. The context of the description of *Ophrys molisana*

Ophrys molisana was described, as its name suggests, from the Molise region. The locus classicus is situated in the municipality of Forlì del Sannio, locality Cese. The collection date is May 27th, 2015.

Fig. 1: *Ophrys molisana*, Italia. Molise (IS). Forlì del Sannio, 08.05.2016, (locus classicus). All photographs Fig. 1-7, 9-28 by R. Soca).

Fig. 2-3: *Ophrys molisana*, Italia, Molise (IS), Forlì del Sannio, 08.05.2016, (locus classicus).

Fig. 4: *Ophrys molisana*

Fig. 5: *Ophrys molisana*

Fig. 6: *O. molisana*. Abruzzo (AQ),
Massa d'Albe, 04.05.2016.

Fig. 7: *O. molisana*. Abruzzo (AQ),
Aielli, 30.05.2016.

An extreme drought was experienced in Italy in spring 2015, especially in the central part of the country. In this region, the poor flowerings took place about one month ahead of the usual dates for the latest ones. The status of the flowerings on June 10th 2015 was similar to July 20th of an average year. The flowerings by the end of May 2015 roughly corresponded to late June in 2013 or 2014. Visiting unfamiliar territories in a poor flowering year is an awkward task, especially with an deficient knowledge of stations, existing taxa and flowering dates. The resulting descriptions can only be denatured. I went to Forlì del Sannio, locality Cese, on May 8th 2016 to check the flowering state. Four plants still had one or two buds, very few plants were still bearing one or two visible flowers, all the other ones were already withered.

3. *Ophrys molisana*: general features

Ophrys molisana, a recently described species (DELFORGE 2015: 18), is an overlooked or rather confusedly interpreted taxon. Thus I am going to try to contribute my knowledge of this taxon to clarify an unclear situation. Its existence is not mentioned in the collective book "Orchidee d'Italia" (GIROS 2016). During various conferences that have been held in 2016 (Ragusa, 31.3.2016; Palena, 4.6.2016), the puzzling questions about this taxon prompted me to provide a better insight into that species.

Ophrys molisana belongs to the *Ophrys aranifera* series. The *Ophrys aranifera* series in the Abruzzo is very complex. ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012: 338-341, 512-519) mention seven undescribed entities. *Ophrys molisana* corresponds to the species referred to as "*Ophrys aranifera* from Popoli" in ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012: 516), that assessment is based on the single photograph shown in the protologue.

Ophrys molisana is the most common species in Abruzzo and Molise. It occurs at elevations ranging from 150 to 1660 m. Its flowering period changes according to elevation. At elevations ranging from 200 to 400 m, blossoming begins in late March-early April; at elevations between 600 and 800 m, the full flowering takes place in early May in the coolest places. One can still come across the species at an elevation of 1660 m in early June.

In Molise, from Isernia to Rionero Sannitico, in the municipalities of Isernia, Forlì del Sannio and Rionero Sannitico, the end of the flowering stage occurs by May 15th in the coolest places, at elevations from 600 to 800 m. We understand why a single surviving plant with two fresh flowers could be spotted at an elevation of 640 m on May 27th of a very dry year, which was definitely a challenge. From Wednesday, May 20th till Saturday, May 23rd,

2015, along with Rolando Romolini, we visited 33 sites around Forlì del Sannio and Ateleta. In this area we have only recorded the presence of *Ophrys aranifera* s.l. in 14 localities, always at elevations above 880 m, never below. Pierre Delforge, in a mail to Amelio Pezzetta (in litt.: 23.3.2016), compared *Ophrys molisana* with *Ophrys brutia*, a different taxon described by the same author. *Ophrys brutia* occurs, not far away from the locus classicus of *Ophrys molisana*, in the North of the Isernia province and the South of the Chieti province.

In the same mail, the descriptor « pense que les mentions d'*O. sphegodes* (sic), d'*O. majellensis* et d'*O. brutia* du Molise et de la Basilicate devraient être reconsidérées: beaucoup d'entre elles appartiennent probablement *O. molisana* ». ["thinks that the mentions of *O. sphegodes* (sic), *O. majellensis* and *O. brutia* from Molise and Basilicata should be reconsidered: many of them probably belong (to) *O. molisana*"], which gives a broad taxinomial and geographical amplitude, but excludes Abruzzo.

"*Ophrys aranifera* from Popoli" (ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 516) is briefly presented: "*Ophrys aranifera* s.l.; very slender plant; fairly large and numerous flowers; speculum simple; appendage rarely present or very small; large notch; very common in Abruzzo and Molise."

Ophrys molisana (type specimen) is described as follows (DELFORGE 2015: 18, in translation): slender plant 36 cm high. Five flowers, belonging to the *Ophrys sphegodes* (sic) group. Greenish lateral sepals 11 × 5 mm, triangular-rounded, hairless wide petals, wavy-edged, apricot-coloured, 7 × 4 mm. Lip 10 × 11 mm (in the flattened out and dried out condition), entire, square to diamond-shaped, soft, red-brown, gibbous, fully surrounded by ivory hairs; rounded off humps 2 mm high; yellowish basal area of the lip; speculum H-shaped, in basal and central position, purple, blue-margined; lip margin narrow with a yellow hue. Stigmatic cavity yellowish green, stained bluish green; pseudo-eyes irregularly bronze-coloured.

4. The detailed morphological characteristics

There are some discrepancies either in the protologue (DELFORGE 2015: 18, 19) or between the protologue and the species data sheet in DELFORGE (2016: 481) and in this one. The discrepancies present in the protologue, between the text and the photograph, are five in number as follows:

- shape of the petals: in the text "petala late triangulares-rotundata" but on the photograph: petals are not triangular and their top is truncated;

- color of the lip hairs: in the text "pilis eburneis" but on the photograph hairs are of the same color as the lip, red-brown;
- basal field: in the text "area basalis labelli helvola" but on the photograph the tint is darker, from light brown to orange-coloured;
- stigmatic cavity: in the text "Cavitas stigmatica flavovirens thalassico maculata" but on the photograph the bluish tint does not exist;
- pseudo-eyes: in the text " pseudo-oculi irregulariter aerei" but on the photograph they are green.

Three divergences between the protologue (DELFORGE 2015: 18, 19) and the data sheet in DELFORGE (2016: 481) are obvious as follows:

- basal field: in the protologue: basal area of the lip yellowish, in Delforge (2016: 481): basal area pale brown, greenish or greenish brown;
- stigmatic cavity: in the protologue: stigmatic cavity yellowish green stained bluish green, in Delforge (2016: 481): stigmatic cavity pale greenish;
- pseudo-eyes: in the protologue: pseudo-eyes bronze-coloured, in Delforge (2016: 481): pseudo-eyes greenish to whitish.

Lastly, contradiction in DELFORGE (2016: 481) between the text and the photograph, the features of the lip hairiness are not consistent with those which we can observe on the photograph: "submarginal pilosity more scattered than that of *O. brutia*, thinned in the distal part" but on the photograph we can clearly see that the pilosity of the distal part is as thick as that of the basal part. The photograph in DELFORGE (2016: 481) is the same as that in the protologue (DELFORGE 2015: 19).

I should also mention that this very common taxon has fairly variable flower features: forty percent of the plants do not have humps; the colour of sepals varies from green to dark red; the colour of petals varies from green to dark red, several forms can be observed: from narrow, with in parallel edges, to quite broad, similar to those of *Ophrys passionis*; the lip is generally entire, very rarely three-lobed; the basal area has generally the same color as the center of the lip or is slightly lighter; the speculum can take up much space, but is never complex; the lip margin colour is not often different from that of the lip; if so, it has a yellowish or very rarely orange colour; hairs are present all around the lip and are usually of the same colour as the lip or lighter; the stigmatic cavity is rounded and visually small in relation to the lip; the pseudo-eyes are round, prominent, green to light brown, most often shiny.

Fig. 8-13: *O. molisana*. Fig. 8-9: Massa d'Albe (AQ), 04.05.2016.

Fig. 10: Campo di Giove. (AQ), 14.06.2014.

Fig. 11: Ortona d. Marsi, 21.05.2014.

Fig. 12: Avezzano (AQ), 21.05.2014.

Fig. 13: Pescara (AQ), 21.05.2014.

5. Distribution in the L'Aquila province (Abruzzo, Italy)

The following list of localities is the outcome of field explorations conducted during the last eleven springs (from 2006 till 2016) in the L'Aquila province. The sites near the limit of the province of L'Aquila in the nearby provinces are mentioned, as well as the place where the species grows at the lowest elevation in the municipality of Celenza sul Trigno (Chieti). Lastly, the locus classicus (the only place known to the descriptor) is mentioned. The localities are arranged in the alphabetical order of municipalities. Some very vast sites have been divided into of 500 meter squares. UTM-coordinates rely on WGS84. All these findings are shown in a map with UTM-10-km grid (fig. 16). The altitudinal frequency is shown in fig. 17.

Fig. 14-15: *Ophrys molisana*, Italia, Abruzzo (AQ). Santo Stefano di Sessanio, 29.05.2016.

Abruzzo - L'Aquila

- Aielli. Cerano. 33T 03840 46601. Alt. 1072 m. 18.05.2014.
- Aielli. Cerano. 33T 03842 46603. Alt. 1124 m. 28.05.2015.
- Aielli. Cerano. 33T 03846 46598. Alt. 1055 m. 11.06.2010. 24.05.2011.
- Aielli. Croce. 33T 03825 46602. Alt. 992 m. 30.05.2012. 20.05.2013. 18.05.2014. 18.04.2016.
- Aielli. Croce. 33T 03827 46603. Alt. 1000 m. 21.05.2011.
- Aielli. La Difesa. 33T 03835 46616. Alt. 1200 m. 21.05.2011.
- Aielli. Prato di Cerro. 33T 03833 46620. Alt. 1300 m. 21.05.2011.
- Aielli. Reniccia. 33T 03826 46605. Alt. 1025 m. 21.05.2011. 18.05.2014.
- Aielli. Reniccia. 33T 03827 46604. Alt. 1031 m. 16.05.2015.
- Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03838 46602. Alt. 1065 m. 18.04.2016.

Fig. 16: Horizontal distribution of *Ophrys molisana* in the L'Aquila province (UTM-10-km grid).

Fig. 17: Vertical distribution of *Ophrys molisana* in the L'Aquila province (number of sites according to elevation).

- Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03842 46600. Alt. 1064 m. 18.05.2014.
 Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03843 46601. Alt. 1098 m. 28.05.2015.
 Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03845 46598. Alt. 1060 m. 07.05.2014.
 Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03846 46598. Alt. 1047 m. 16.05.2015.
 Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03846 46599. Alt. 1064 m. 18.05.2014.
 Aielli. Valle di Cupoli. 33T 03815 46584. Alt. 830 m. 23.05.2011.
 Alfedena. Colle Jaratto. 33T 04178 46209. Alt. 1110 m. 03.05.2013.
 Ateleta. Colle Valgelata. 33T 04327 46339. Alt. 834 m. 14.05.2007. 25.05.2011.
 Ateleta. Masseria Rossi. 33T 04344 46343. Alt. 840 m. 02.06.2016.
 Ateleta. Teresella. 33T 04342 46341. Alt. 829 m. 07.06.2010. 25.05.2011.
 Avezzano. Borgo Pineta. 33T 03691 46561. Alt. 721 m. 03.05.2014. 24.05.2016.
 Avezzano. Macerino Vecchio. 33T 03695 46581. Alt. 797 m. 05.05.2014.
 Avezzano. Monte d'Aria. 33T 03677 46528. Alt. 886 m. 18.04.2016.
 Avezzano. Monte Salviano. 33T 03673 46539 / 33T 03673 46540 / 33T 03669
 46553. Alt. 1007 m / 1023 m / 1064 m. 21.04.2013.
 Avezzano. Monte Santa Felice. 33T 03657 46564 / 33T 03657 46563. Alt. 985 m /
 975 m. 16.04.2015.
 Avezzano. Noceleone. 33T 03702 46582. Alt. 805 m. 05.05.2014.
 Avezzano. Palombara. 33T 03686 46586. Alt. 875 m. 07.05.2014.
 Avezzano. Santuario Madonna Pietracquaria. 33T 03673 46539. Alt. 950 m.
 24.05.2011.
 Avezzano. Santuario Madonna Pietracquaria. 33T 03673 46539. Alt. 1007 m.
 30.05.2012. 05.05.2014.
 Avezzano. Tre Conche. 33T 03691 46566. Alt. 730 m. 03.05.2014.
 Barisciano. Cima della Selva. 33T 03871 46872 / 33T 03873 46870. Alt. 1230 m /
 1232 m. 12.05.2007.
 Barisciano. Vadesprina. 33T 03837 46880. Alt. 1100 m. 19.05.2011.
 Barrea. I Fossati. 33T 04164 46211 / 33T 04164 46213 / 33T 04165 46213. Alt. 879
 m / 1116 m / 1145 m. 08.06.2010.
 Barrea. I Fossati. 33T 04164 46214. Alt. 1160 m. 03.05.2013. 25.05.2014.
 Bisegna. Monte del Calvario. 33T 03970 46443. Alt. 1065 m. 19.05.2014.
 Bisegna. Pratone. 33T 03962 46470. Alt. 982 m. 12.06.2014.
 Cagnano Amiterno. Costa Lupo. 33T 03547 47035. Alt. 824 m. 07.06.2014.
 Calascio. Colle Duro. 33T 03940 46855. Alt. 939 m. 22.04.2006.
 Calascio. Maccaragna. 33T 03951 46851. Alt. 830 m. 22.04.2006.
 Calascio. Rocca Calascio. 33T 03921 46872. Alt. 1300 m. 13.05.2007.
 Campo di Giove. Collelardo. 33T 04234 46464. Alt. 1230 m. 02.06.2016.
 Campotosto. Cesa Spizzica. 33T 03660 47083. Alt. 1332 m. 07.06.2014.
 Campotosto. Cesa Spizzica. 33T 03661 47087. Alt. 1338 m. 07.06.2014.
 Capestrano. Colle Frivello. 33T 04009 46786. Alt. 333 m. 08.04.2013. 15.04.2015.
 Capestrano. Francesconi. 33T 03963 46805. Alt. 424 m. 22.04.2006. 14.04.2015.
 Capestrano. Francesconi. 33T 03967 46808. Alt. 432 m. 14.04.2015.
 Capestrano. Francesconi. 33T 03974 46814. Alt. 428 m. 14.04.2015.
 Capestrano. La Torretta. 33T 03992 46793. Alt. 430 m. 08.04.2013.
 Capestrano. Poggio della Cisterna. 33T 03974 46801. Alt. 445 m. 14.04.2015.

- Castel di Sangro. Cipollone. 33T 04258 46286 / 33T 04259 46288. Alt. 849 m / 879 m. 23.05.2015.
- Castel di Sangro. Cipollone. 33T 04258 46287. Alt. 861 m. 12.06.2014.
- Castel di Sangro. Cipollone. 33T 04258 46292 / 33T 04260 46289. Alt. 913 m / 901 m. 12.06.2014.
- Castelvecchio Calvisio. Capramorta. 33T 03899 46841. Alt. 1028 m. 15.05.2015.
- Cocullo. Costa Fra Angelo. 33T 03990 46528. Alt. 800 m. 20.05.2011.
- Collepietro. Colle Rotondo. 33T 04009 46749. Alt. 713 m. 15.04.2015.
- Collepietro. Contrada Vigna Vecchia. 33T 03992 46742. Alt. 728 m. 15.04.2015.
- Collepietro. Contrada Vigna Vecchia. 33T 03999 46740. Alt. 759 m. 12.05.2014.
- Collepietro. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04009 46716 / 33T 04009 46717. Alt. 654 m / 652 m. 10.05.2007.
- Collepietro. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04009 46716. Alt. 650 m. 28.04.2002.
- Collepietro. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04009 46715. Alt. 646 m. 20.05.2011. 08.04.2012. 05.05.2012. 20.04.2013. 06.05.2013.
- Collepietro. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04009 46716. Alt. 656 m. 22.04.2006. 12.04.2015.
- Collepietro. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04009 46716. Alt. 652 m. 12.05.2014. 15.04.2016.
- Collepietro. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04009 46716 / 33T 04010 46717. Alt. 649 m / 666 m. 03.05.2010.
- Collepietro. Santa Rosa. 33T 03997 46727. Alt. 766 m. 03.05.2010. 20.05.2011. 5.05.2012. 12.05.2014. 15.04.2015.
- Gioia dei Marsi. Castelluccia. 33T 03923 46445. Alt. 727 m. 08.05.2014.
- Gioia dei Marsi. Cupo di Ferrone. 33T 03932 46421. Alt. 1137 m. 09.06.2010.
- Gioia dei Marsi. La Perazza. 33T 03937 46407. Alt. 1322 m. 09.06.2010.
- Gioia dei Marsi. Monticelli. 33T 03926 46427. Alt. 1034 m. 09.06.2010.
- L'Aquila. Camporanero. 33T 03749 46997. Alt. 1168 m. 07.06.2014.
- L'Aquila. Fori le Sacquera. 33T 03787 46981. Alt. 1085 m. 07.06.2014.
- L'Aquila / Lucoli. Colle Ripa. 33T 03627 46879. Alt. 921 m. 20.05.2014.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Cima Piange. 33T 03599 46652. Alt. 927 m. 11.05.2014.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Cima Piange. 33T 03600 46650. Alt. 911 m. 17.05.2015.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Cima Piange. 33T 03601 46650. Alt. 941 m. 11.05.2014.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Le Coste. 33T 03613 46648. Alt. 1026 m. 21.05.2011. 06.05.2012. 04.05.2013. 04.05.2014. 12.05.2015. 02.05.2016.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Marciano. 33T 03660 46620. Alt. 800 m. 11.05.2014.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Monte Cativiglia. 33T 03618 46677 / 33T 03617 46677. Alt. 1266 m / 1238 m. 06.05.2012.
- Magliano dei Marsi. Pianura di Campo. 33T 03618 46656. Alt. 1063 m. 21.05.2011. 06.05.2012. 04.05.2013. 04.05.2014. 12.05.2015. 02.05.2016.
- Massa d'Albe. Alba Fucens. 33T 03686 46592. Alt. 919 m. 07.05.2014.
- Massa d'Albe. Alba Fucens. 33T 03687 46595. Alt. 960 m. 05.05.2014.
- Massa d'Albe. Forma Rotta. 33T 03740 46631. Alt. 1084 m. 17.06.2014. 02.05.2016.
- Massa d'Albe. I Valloni. 33T 03668 46641. Alt. 960 m. 13.05.2007.

Massa d'Albe. I Valloni. 33T 03670 46646. Alt. 1065 m. 17.05.2016.
 Massa d'Albe. La Lave. 33T 03660 46642. Alt. 1010 m. 27.05.2016.
 Massa d'Albe. La Lave. 33T 03668 46641. Alt. 963 m. 22.05.2011.
 Massa d'Albe. Le Cese. 33T 03723 46635. Alt. 1146 m. 15.04.2016.
 Massa d'Albe. Mainucci. 33T 03704 46620. Alt. 954 m. 14.05.2015.
 Massa d'Albe. Santa Maria degli Albenzi. 33T 03691 46614. Alt. 922 m.
 16.05.2016.
 Massa d'Albe. Valenti. 33T 03740 46631. Alt. 1012 m. 17.06.2014. 02.05.2016.
 Massa d'Albe. Valle Majelama. 33T 03695 46648. Alt. 1140 m. 17.05.2016.
 Montereale. Vigne. 33T 03571 47141. Alt. 982 m. 08.06.2014.
 Navelli. La Serra di Navelli. 33T 03960 46776. Alt. 692 m. 22.04.2006.
 Navelli. Voltata San Giovanni. 33T 03969 46792. Alt. 652 m. 09.04.2012.
 Navelli. Voltata San Giovanni. 33T 03970 46792. Alt. 661 m. 12.04.2015.
 Navelli. Voltata San Giovanni. 33T 03970 46792. Alt. 652 m. 07.04.2013.
 20.04.2013. 15.04.2016.
 Ofena. Colle Troilo. 33T 03969 46832. Alt. 400 m. 14.04.2015.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Accodino. 33T 03960 46480. Alt. 937 m. 19.05.2014.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 03946 46515. Alt. 950 m. 13.05.2014.
 14.05.2015. 16.04.2016.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Costa di Pleia. 33T 03953 46524. Alt. 1095 m. 14.05.2015.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Fonnelle. 33T 03950 46522. Alt. 1008 m. 21.05.2014. 14.05.2015.
 19.05.2016.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03946 46516. Alt. 929 m. 13.05.2014.
 14.05.2015. 16.04.2016.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Scrimone. 33T 03960 46492. Alt. 1018 m. 19.05.2014.
 Ortona dei Marsi. Verrella. 33T 03954 46485 / 33T 03954 46485. Alt. 965 m / 1001
 m. 19.05.2014.
 Ovindoli. Forma Rotta. 33T 03743 46637. Alt. 1294 m. 04.06.2015.
 Ovindoli. Fornace. 33T 03746 46630. Alt. 1091 m. 18.05.2016.
 Pacentro. Pian dell'Orso. 33T 04190 46561. Alt. 1049 m. 16.05.2014.
 Pescina. Ponte della Valle. 33T 03898 46545. Alt. 1025 m. 20.05.2011. 19.05.2014.
 Pescina. Rapacica. 33T 03893 46547. Alt. 859 m. 12.05.2015. 17.04.2016.
 Pescina. Rapacica. 33T 03893 46547. Alt. 865 m. 19.05.2014.
 Pizzoli. Cava Rossa. 33T 03648 47025. Alt. 1296 m. 26.05.2015.
 Raiano. Il Castellone. 33T 04009 46622. Alt. 472 m. 11.04.2015.
 Rivisondoli. Colle Magnattaro. 33T 04263 46324. Alt. 1350 m. 26.05.2011.
 13.06.2014.
 Rivisondoli. Colle Pugnares. 33T 04266 46322. Alt. 1340 m. 26.05.2011.
 13.06.2014.
 Rivisondoli. Paduli. 33T 04262 46324. Alt. 1320 m. 26.05.2011. 13.06.2014.
 Roccaraso. Contrada Barone. 33T 04289 46337. Alt. 1142 m. 19.06.2010.
 25.05.2011.
 Roccaraso. Contrada Barone. 33T 04289 46337. Alt. 1155 m. 13.06.2014.
 23.05.2015. 23.05.2016.
 Roccaraso. La Gravara. 33T 04299 46338. Alt. 1041 m. 25.05.2011.

- Roccaraso. Monticelli. 33T 04282 46333. Alt. 1244 m. 25.05.2011. 09.05.2014.
 Roccaraso. Vicenne. 33T 04277 46332. Alt. 1265 m. 25.05.2011.
 San Benedetto in Perillis. Monte Croce (face nord). 33T 03987 46722. Alt. 830 m. 12.05.2014.
 San Benedetto in Perillis. Monte Croce. 33T 03997 46726. Alt. 757 m. 03.05.2010. 20.05.2011. 05.05.2012. 12.05.2014. 15.04.2015.
 San Benedetto in Perillis. Monte Croce (face est). 33T 03999 46725. Alt. 732 m. 15.04.2016.
 San Benedetto in Perillis. Monte Croce. 33T 04009 46715. Alt. 660 m. 28.04.2002. 22.04.2006. 10.05.2007. 03.05.2010. 20.05.2011. 08.04.2012. 05.05.2012. 20.04.2013. 06.05.2013. 12.05.2014. 12.04.2015. 15.04.2016.
 San Benedetto in Perillis. Monte Ospedalera. 33T 04006 46711. Alt. 595 m. 15.04.2015.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Cima delle Serre. 33T 03888 46901. Alt. 1445 m. 19.05.2011.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Cima delle Serre. 33T 03890 46897. Alt. 1427 m. 29.05.2016.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Cima di Refana. 33T 03892 46894. Alt. 1371 m. 09.06.2014.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Colle Sparviero. 33T 03890 46911. Alt. 1444 m. 09.06.2014.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Colle Sparviero. 33T 03891 46911. Alt. 1514 m. 29.05.2016.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Monte Cecco d'Antonio. 33T 03898 46931 / 33T 03896 46930. Alt. 1620 m / 1652 m. 29.05.2016.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Valle Fresca. 33T 03893 46919. Alt. 1563 m. 09.06.2014.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Valle Fresca. 33T 03894 46919. Alt. 1554 m. 29.05.2016.
 Santo Stefano di Sessanio. Valle Fresca. 33T 03898 46915 / 33T 03899 46916 / 33T 03898 46915. Alt. 1533 m / 1525 m / 1530 m. 09.06.2014.
 Scanno. San Leonardo. 33T 04077 46379. Alt. 1160 m. 08.06.2010.
 Sulmona. Vallone di Grascito. 33T 04124 46543. Alt. 443 m. 20.05.2014. 11.05.2015.
 Tagliacozzo. Monte La Difesa. 33T 03549 46572. Alt. 1034 m. 28.05.2014.
 Villa Santa Lucia Degli Abruzzi. Colle di Musco. 33T 03980 46893. Alt. 1068 m. 16.05.2014.

Abruzzo - Chieti

- Celenza sul Trigno. Pinciarelle. 33T 04672 46361. Alt. 148 m. 11.04.2015.
 Lettopalena. Cesa Piana. 33T 04325 46477. Alt. 1005 m. 15.05.2014.
 Montenerodomo. Juvanum. 33T 04378 46499. Alt. 979 m. 12.05.2015. 07.05.2016.
 Palena. Colleminozzi. 33T 04283 46491. Alt. 818 m. 15.06.2014.
 Palena. Cotte. 33T 04304 46481. Alt. 897 m. 15.05.2014. 12.05.2015.
 Palena. Girone. 33T 04273 46461. Alt. 906 m. 06.06.2010. 26.05.2011.
 Palena. Ponte Sarrigone. 33T 04296 46485. Alt. 812 m. 15.05.2014.
 Palena. San Cataldo. 33T 04269 46467. Alt. 941 m. 07.05.2016.

Palena. San Cataldo. 33T 04270 46463. Alt. 890 m. 28.04.2002.
Palena. San Cataldo. 33T 04271 46462 / 33T 04270 46466. Alt. 855 m / 932 m.
06.06.2010. 26.05.2011.
Sant'Eufemia A Maiella. Fosso Vetrina. 33T 04193 46629. Alt. 930 m. 06.05.2016.

Abruzzo - Pescara

Bussi sul Tirino. Valle della Madona. 33T 04018 46761. Alt. 404 m. 15.04.2015.
Popoli. Capo Pescara. 33T 04026 46687. Alt. 263 m. 12.04.2015.
Popoli. Castiglione. 33T 04029 46707. Alt. 367 m. 22.04.2006.
Popoli. Cerro. 33T 04014 46676. Alt. 367 m. 12.04.2015.
Popoli. Fonte Borromeo. 33T 04041 46705. Alt. 249 m. 22.04.2006.
Popoli. Fonte Borromeo. 33T 04042 46707. Alt. 250 m. 22.04.2006.
Popoli. Fonte Borromeo. 33T 04044 46711. Alt. 261 m. 10.05.2007. 20.05.2011.
05.05.2012.
Popoli. Lettopiano. 33T 04029 46712. Alt. 419 m. 05.05.2012. 06.05.2013.
12.04.2015.
Popoli. Spallone. 33T 04025 46712. Alt. 390 m. 28.04.2002. 22.04.2006.

Abruzzo - Teramo

Pietracamela. Tufaro. 33T 03821 47078. Alt. 1327 m. 21.06.2014.

Molise - Isernia

Castel del Giudice. Colle Castellana. 33T 04372 46350. Alt. 891 m. 07.05.2016.
Forli del Sannio. Cese. (locus classicus) 33T 04320 46150. Alt. 650 m. 19.04.2012.
02.05.2013. 08.05.2016.
Forli del Sannio. Colle Manicone. 33T 04303 46157. Alt. 798 m. 02.05.2010.
Forli del Sannio. Macchia. 33T 04312 46144. Alt. 730 m. 02.05.2010.
Forli del Sannio. Macchia. 33T 04315 46140. Alt. 696 m. 02.05.2010.
San Pietro Avellana. Bosco della Difesa Grande. 33T 04324 46279. Alt. 910 m.
23.05.2016.
Roccasicura. Ponte del Maltempo. 33T 04381 46171. Alt. 868 m. 02.05.2010.

Lazio - Roma

Orvinio. Pratarella. 33T 03274 46672 / 33T 03272 46670. Alt. 887 m / 895 m.
09.05.2007. 15.05.1999. 25.05.2016.

6. Herbarium specimens

Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Capestrano. Francesconi. 33T 03974 46814. Alt. 428 m.
14.04.2015. RS.2015.404; Massa d'Albe. Valle Majelama. 33T 03695 46648.
Alt. 1143 m. 17.05.2016. RS.2016.503; Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T

03947 46514. Alt. 966 m. 19.05.2016. RS.2016.505; Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03946 46516. Alt. 950 m. 19.05.2014. RS.2014.520; Pescina. Rapacica. 33T 03893 46547. Alt. 865 m. 19.05.2014. RS.2014.510; RS.2014.511; RS.2014.512; RS.2014.513; RS.2014.514; RS.2014.515; RS.2014.516; Roccaraso. Contrada Barone. 33T 04289 46337. Alt. 1149 m. 23.05.2015. RS.2015.508; RS.2015.509; RS.2015.510.

All these specimens were collected by the author and deposited in the Herbarium Universitatis Florentinae Natural History Museum Firenze (FI).

7. Descriptions of three hybrids

7.1. *Ophrys* × *milioniae* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

Ophrys dinarica Kranjčev & P.Delforge × *Ophrys molisana* P.Delforge

Descriptio: planta 34 cm alta; folia basalia: 6; flores: 8; sepala oblonga lanceolata, viridia; petala triangulata elongata, viridia roseo suffuso, marginibus undulatis cum albidis pilis; labellum integrum valde convexum, quadrangulatum elongatum, brunneo fusco, castaneo pilis magnis cinctum, leviter gibbosum; macula magna, complexa, castanea, marginea albida flava cincta; labelli appendix magna lataque, erecta antierius versus, flavo-viridis; inferiora labelli parte brunneo; cava stigmatica atrobrunnea; pseudo-oculi viridia; connectivum obtusum; moles polliniferae luteae. Floret: fine majore principio junio mense.

Diagnosis: hic specimen inserere illos diceret parentis optimi speciem, quae haud procul credebant. Hybrida idem potest per naturam, colores mensurisque, quantam prima generatio hybridi. Omnes partes flos medius inter parentes perfecte et plene concepto.

Holotypus: Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03945 46516. Alt. 941 m. 26.05.2014. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2014.521.

Etymology: ex nomine "Milionia", nomen vetus Ortona dei Marsi, ubi reperta, hybrida nominatur.

Description: plant 34 cm high; 6 basal leaves; 8 flowers; sepals elongate, lanceolate, green; petals triangular elongate, green suffused with pink at the base, wavy-edged, provided with white marginal hairs; lip entire, highly convex, quadrangular elongate, dark brown, fringed with reddish brown marginal hairs; humps low; speculum large, complex, reddish brown surrounded with a broad yellowish white line; appendage prominent and broad, forwardly directed, yellowish green; basal area brown; stigmatic cavity

blackish brown; pseudo-eyes green; column connective obtuse; pollinia yellow; flowering in late May – early June.

Etymology: from Milonia, former name of Ortona dei Marsi, the municipality from where the plant is described.

Iconography: in hoc op.: Fig. 18-21.

Specimina selecta: Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Aielli. Croce. 33T 03825 46603. Alt. 990 m. 24.05.2016. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2016.508; 30.05.2016. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2016.509.

Geographical distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ, CH, PE), Molise (IS).

Personal discoveries: Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila.

Aielli. Cerano. 33T 03846 46598. Alt. 1055 m. 11.06.2010;
 Aielli. Croce. 33T 03825 46603. Alt. 990 m. 24.05.2016. 30.05.2016;
 Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03843 46601. Alt. 1093 m. 28.05.2015;
 Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03846 46599. Alt. 1064 m. 18.05.2014;
 Ateleta. Masseria Rossi. 33T 04342 46343. Alt. 839 m. 02.06.2016;
 Barrea. I Fossati. 33T 04164 46213. Alt. 1145 m. 25.05.2014. 23.05.2016;
 Collepietro. Monte Ospedamera. 33T 04009 46715. Alt. 646 m. 05.05.2012;
 Massa d'Albe. I Valloni. 33T 03668 46641. Alt. 960 m. 13.05.2007;
 Massa d'Albe. I Valloni. 33T 03669 46645. Alt. 1040 m. 17.05.2016;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 03947 46515. Alt. 950 m. 13.05.2014;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 03947 46515. Alt. 964 m. 14.05.2015;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 03947 46514. Alt. 964 m. 19.05.2016;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 0394746514. Alt. 964 m. 19.05.2014;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 03947 46516. Alt. 957 m. 19.05.2014;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Colle Pallettera. 33T 03947 46514. Alt. 966 m. 19.05.2016;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03945 46516. Alt. 940 m. 14.05.2015;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03945 46516. Alt. 941 m. 19.05.2016;
 Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03945 46516. Alt. 941 m. 19.05.2014.
 26.05.2014;
 Pescara. Ponte della Valle. 33T 03895 46546. Alt. 852 m. 19.05.2014;
 Pescara. Rapacica. 33T 03895 46546. Alt. 857 m. 19.05.2016;
 Roccaraso. Vicenne. 33T 04277 46332. Alt. 1265 m. 25.05.2011;
 Abruzzo. Chieti. Sant'Eufemia A Maiella. Fosso Vetrina. 33T 04193 46629.
 Alt. 930 m. 06.05.2016;
 Abruzzo. Pescara. Popoli. Lettopiano. 33T 04029 46712. Alt. 419 m.
 05.05.2012;
 Molise. Isernia. San Pietro Avellana. Bosco della Difesa Grande. 33T 04324
 46279. Alt. 910 m. 27.05.2011. 18.05.2012. 10.05.2014.

Fig. 18-19: *Ortona dei Marsi* (AQ), 21.05.2014 (fig. 18: holotypus).

Fig. 18-21: *Ophrys dinarica* × *O. molisana* (*O. ×millioniae*).
Fig. 20: Pescina (AQ), 26.05.2014; fig. 21: Ortona dei Marsi (AQ), 21.05.2014.

Orchids occurring on the site where the type grows on May 13th and 19th, 2014:

Aceras anthropophorum, *Ophrys apifera*, *O. appennina*, *O. aranifera* of Navelli, *O. dinarica*, *O. gracilis*, *O. molisana*, *O. pinguis*, *O. promontorii*, *O. riojana*, *O. romolinii*, *O. apifera* × *O. dinarica* (1), *O. apifera* × *O. molisana* (1), *O. appennina* × *O. dinarica* (3), *O. dinarica* × *O. molisana* (12), *O. dinarica* × *O. riojana* (1), *O. gracilis* × *O. pinguis* (3), *Orchis morio*, *O. purpurea*, *O. tridentata*, *O. ustulata*, *O. laxiflora* × *O. morio* (1), *Serapias parviflora*, *S. vomeracea* subsp. *longipetala*.

Remarks: the described hybrid grew along with another eleven hybrids resulting from the same crossing, albeit not quite identical to the described specimen. This specimen has features best matching those of the parent species, both of which were growing a short distance away. The hybrids could be identified, by their features, colours and dimensions, as first generation hybrids. All the flower parts were perfectly intermediate between those of both parents, them in full anthesis too.

7.2. *Ophrys* × *rasinii* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

Ophrys insectifera L. × *Ophrys molisana* P.Delforge

Descriptio: planta 51 cm alta; folia basalia: 6; flores: 14; sepala oblonga lanceolata, viridia, sepalum dorsalum marginibus implicatis; petala elongata, prope parallelibus marginibus, bruneo castaneo; labellum trilobum, convexum, nigricum, lobo mediano trapezoideum; macula quadrangulata-formis ad basin labelli; inferiora labelli parte nigricans; cava stigmatica nigricans; pseudo-oculi nigri; connectivum obtusum breveque; moles polliniferae luteae aurantiacae. Floret: majo.

Diagnosis: electo specimen optimi parentis vultus species, quae haud procul crescebant. Idem potest per proprietates, colores mensurasque, quantam prima generatio hybridi. Omnes partes flos medius inter parentes perfecte et etiam quoque florente.

Holotypus: Italia. Abruzzo. L’Aquila. Roccaraso. Contrada Barone. 33T 04289 46337. Alt. 1149 m. 23.05.2015. Coll. R. Romolini et R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2015.513.

Etymology: ex nomine loci “Roccaraso”, quod est nomen fluvius Rasinus, unde Rocca Rasini, ubi reperta, hybrida nominatur.

Description: plant 51 cm high; 6 basal leaves; 14 flowers; sepals elongate lanceolate, green, dorsal sepal with rolled-up edges; petals elongate with nearly parallel edges, reddish brown; lip three-lobed, convex, blackish, median lobe trapezoidal; speculum roughly square-shaped, occupying the base of the lip,

blackish brown; basal area blackish; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes dark; column connective short and obtuse; pollinia orangy yellow; flowering in May.

Etymology: from Roccaraso municipality, from where the plant is described, which derives its name from the river Rasinus, whence Rocca Rasini.

Iconography: in hoc op.: Fig. 22-23.

Specimina selecta: Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Roccaraso. Contrada Barone. 33T 04289 46337. Alt. 1149 m. 23.05.2015. Coll. R. Romolini & R. Soca, sub No. RR. 27/2015 (FI).

Geographical distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ).

Personal discoveries: Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Roccaraso. Contrada Barone. 33T 04289 46337. Alt. 1155 m. 13.06.2014.

Orchids occurring on the site where the type grows: *Anacamptis pyramidalis*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *C. longifolia*, *Dactylorhiza saccifera*, *Gymnadenia conopsea*, *Ophrys apifera*, *O. dinarica*, *O. insectifera*, *O. lucana*, *O. molisana*, *O. insectifera* × *O. molisana* (7), *Orchis morio*, *O. purpurea*, *Serapias parviflora*.

Remarks: the described hybrid grew along with another six hybrids resulting from the same crossing, albeit not quite identical to the described specimen. This specimen has features best matching those of the parent species, both of which were growing a short distance away. The hybrids could be identified, by their features, colours and dimensions, as first generation hybrids. All the flower parts were perfectly intermediate between those of both parents, them in full anthesis too.

Fig. 22: *O. x rasinii*.

Fig. 22-23: *Ophrys insectifera* × *O. molisana* (*O. x rasinii*), Abruzzo, Roccaraso (AQ), 23.05.2015 (holotypus);
fig. 24: *O. molisana*, S. Stefano Sessanio (AQ), 29.05.2016.

Fig. 25-26: *Ophrys molisana* × *O. romolinii* (*O. x fucinis*), holotypus.

Fig. 27-28: *Ophrys molisana* × *O. romolinii* (*O. x fucinis*), Abruzzo, Avezzano (AQ). Fig. 25-26: 07.05.2014; fig. 27-28: 11.05.2014.

7.3. *Ophrys* × *fucinis* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

Ophrys molisana P.Delforge × *Ophrys romolinii* Soca

Descriptio: planta 16 cm alta; folia basalia: 6; flores: 3; sepala oblonga lanceolata, viridia; petala triangulata elongata, cinnabarino, marginibus undulatis cum albidis pilis; labellum integrum convexum, quadrangulatum elongatum, nigricans, castaneo pilis magnis cinctum, leviter gibbosum; macula duabis lineis elongatis crassis parallelibus, castaneo; labelli appendix parva, triangulata, erecta antierius versus, distincte lacinia includum; inferiora labelli parte nigricans; cava stigmatica nigricans; pseudo-oculi nigricans; connectivum obtusum breveque; moles polliniferae luteae. Floret: majo.

Diagnosis: delecto specimen optimi parentis congruens species, quae haud procul crescebant. Idem potest per signos, colores mensurasque, quantam prima generatio hybridi. Omnes partes flos medius inter parentes perfecte et etiam quoque plene concepto.

Holotypus: Italia. Abruzzo. L’Aquila. Avezzano. Palombara. 33T 03686 46589. Alt. 901 m. 7.05.2014. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2014.501.

Etymology: ex nomine loci “Fucinis” (Alba Fucinis) ubi reperta, hybrida nominatur. Alba Fucens (Regione IV) quod secundum latinam coloniam in agrum equi saeculis condita CCCIII BC. Quae est de tabula a monte Massa d’Albe. Is cum Soram (Regione I) capere initium Marsi incrementa finibus suis obvia.

Description: plant 16 cm high; 6 basal leaves; 3 flowers; sepals oblong lanceolate, green; petals elongate triangular, reddish orangy, wavy-edged, provided with white marginal hairs; lip entire, convex, quadrangular elongate, blackish, fringed with dense reddish brown hairs; humps low; speculum comprising two parallel thick lines, crossing the lip longitudinally, reddish brown; appendage small, triangular, greenish, forwardly-directed, inserted within a very deep notch; basal area blackish; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes dark; column connective short and obtuse; pollinia yellow; flowering in May.

Etymology: From (*Alba Fucinis*) Alba Fucens (Regio IV) which is the second Latin colony on the Eque territory, founded in 303 before our era. It lies on the plateau of a hill of the municipality of Massa d’Albe. It was, together with Sora (Regio I), the first attempt to stop the expansion of Marsi by encircling their territory.

Iconography: in hoc op.: Fig. 25-28.

Specimina selecta: Italia. Abruzzo. L’Aquila. Avezzano. Palombara. 33T 03686 46589. Alt. 901 m. 07.05.2014. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2014.502. (FI); Italia. Abruzzo. L’Aquila. Aielli. Croce.

33T 03825 46603. Alt. 992 m. 24.05.2016. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2016.506; 30.05.2016. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub No. RS.2016.507; Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Massa d'Albe. Valle Majelama. 33T 03695 46648. Alt. 1143 m. 17.05.2016. Coll. R. Soca. Cons. in herb. FI. sub n° RS.2016.504.

Geographical distribution in Italy (obs. pers.): Abruzzo (AQ, CH, PE).

Personal discoveries: Italia. Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Aielli. Cerano. 33T 03846 46598. Alt. 1055 m. 11.06.2010; Aielli. Croce. 33T 03825 46603. Alt. 992 m. 24.05.2016. 30.05.2016; Aielli. Reniccia. 33T 03826 46605. Alt. 1038 m. 18.05.2014; Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03843 46599. Alt. 1059 m. 24.05.2016; Avezzano. Palombara. 33T 03686 46589. Alt. 901 m. 07.05.2014; Collepietro. Monte Ospedamera. 33T 04009 46716. Alt. 652 m. 12.05.2014; Massa d'Albe. Valle Majelama. 33T 03695 46648 / 33T 03695 46648. Alt. 1140 m / 1143 m. 17.05.2016; Rivisondoli. Colle Pugnarese. 33T 04266 46322. Alt. 1340 m. 26.05.2011; Abruzzo. Chieti. Montenerodomo. Juvanum. 33T 04378 46497. Alt. 974 m. 12.05.2015; Palena. San Cataldo. 33T 04271 46462. Alt. 859 m. 26.05.2011; Abruzzo. Pescara. Popoli. Lettopiano. 33T 04029 46712. Alt. 419 m. 05.05.2012.

Orchids occurring on the site where the type grows: *Aceras anthropophorum*, *Cephalanthera damasonium*, *Himantoglossum adriaticum*, *Ophrys dinarica*, *O. funerea*, *O. incubacea*, *O. molisana*, *O. riojana*, *O. romolinii*, *O. incubacea* × *O. molisana* (2), *O. molisana* × *O. romolinii* (15), *Orchis morio*, *O. purpurea*, *O. tridentata*.

Remarks: the described hybrid grew along with another fourteen hybrids resulting from the same crossing, albeit not quite identical to the described specimen. This specimen has features best matching those of the parent species, both of which were growing a short distance away. The hybrids could be identified, by their features, colours and dimensions, as first generation hybrids. All the flower parts were perfectly intermediate between those of both parents, them in full anthesis too.

8. Other known hybrids with *Ophrys molisana*

8.1 *Ophrys apifera* × *O. molisana*.

Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Ortona dei Marsi. Pratolungo. 33T 03945 46516. Alt. 942 m. 19.05.2014.

8.2 *Ophrys exaltata* subsp. *archipelagi* × *O. molisana*.

Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Navelli. Voltata San Giovanni. 33T 03970 46792. Alt. 661 m. 12.04.2015.

8.3 *Ophrys incubacea* × *O. molisana*.

Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Aielli. Cerano. 33T 03846 46598. Alt. 1055 m. 11.06.2010; Aielli. Reniccia. 33T 03827 46604. Alt. 1031 m. 16.05.2015; Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03847 46599. Alt. 1061 m. 16.05.2015; Avezzano. Palombara. 33T 03686 46586. Alt. 875 m. 07.05.2014; Collepietro. Monte Ospedalerà. 33T 04009 46717. Alt. 655 m. 12.05.2014; Massa d'Albe. Alba Fucens. 33T 03686 46592. Alt. 919 m. 07.05.2014; Pescina. Ponte della Valle. 33T 03898 46545. Alt. 1025 m. 20.05.2011.

8.4 *Ophrys molisana* × *O. promontorii*.

Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Barrea. I Fossati. 33T 04164 46214. Alt. 1167 m. 08.05.2014; Barrea. I Fossati. 33T 04165 46212. Alt. 1129 m. 03.05.2013; Capestrano. S. Pelagia. 33T 03963 46805. Alt. 424 m. 22.04.2006; Collepietro. Monte Ospedalerà. 33T 04009 46715. Alt. 646 m. 20.04.2013; Navelli. Voltata San Giovanni. 33T 03970 46793. Alt. 669 m. 20.04.2013; Raiano. Il Castellone. 33T 04010 46622. Alt. 478 m. 11.04.2015; Rivisondoli. Colle Pugnaresè. 33T 04266 46322. Alt. 1340 m. 26.05.2011. Abruzzo. Chieti. Palena. Girone. 33T 04273 46462. Alt. 909 m. 26.05.2011; Palena. Ponte Sarrigone. 33T 04297 46486. Alt. 823 m. 15.05.2014; Molise. Isernia. Rionero Sannitico. Costa Cavallo. 33T 04269 46204. Alt. 957 m. 02.05.2013.

Remark: ROSSI & MINUTILLO (1989) described a hybrid *Ophrys aranifera* s.l. × *O. promontorii* (*Ophrys* × *terrae-laboris* W.Rossi & Minutillo, Webbia 43(2): 352-353. 1989), the parent «*aranifera*» is certainly *O. ausonia*. The place and date indicated incite this analysis. [Italia] Lazio meridionale, M.ti Aurunci, M. Revole, versante SE, 800 m circa, su gariga calcarea, 01.05.1985, W. Rossi et F. Minutillo » (FI).

8.5 *Ophrys molisana* × *O. riojana*.

Abruzzo. L'Aquila. Aielli. Strepata. 33T 03839 46601. Alt. 1072 m. 18.04.2016; Collepietro. Colle Rotondo. 33T 04009 46749. Alt. 713 m. 15.04.2015; Navelli. Voltata San Giovanni. 33T 03969 46792. Alt. 641 m. 15.04.2016.

Conclusions

Many zones remain to be prospected in the province of Aquila to perfect the knowledge of *Ophrys molisana*. It remains of course also to expand the surveys to provinces and neighbouring regions for a better understanding of the geographical area of distribution of this species. It would be a good starting point for a better comprehension of the *Araniferae* series in central Italy.

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